

GRAPHENE OXIDE/GRAPHITE NANOSHEETS COMPOSITE THIN FILMS FOR WEARABLE STRAIN SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Facile fabrication of highly flexible and sensitive strain sensors is essential for emerging applications such as wearable electronics. Nanomaterials have been extensively explored as sensing elements to fabricate highly sensitive and stretchable strain sensors. Unfortunately, it is still a formidable challenge to develop a facile, low-cost, scalable approach to fabricate ultrasensitive strain sensors with excellent stretchability. Graphite nanosheets (GNs) consisting of multilayered graphene with a high electrical conductivity offer potential to producing wearable strain sensors at low cost due to its large-scale process *via* intercalation and expansion of natural graphite. We utilize the readily available graphene oxide (GO) and GNs as sensing materials to fabricate high-performance strain sensors using a simple, cost-effective and solution processable strategy. It is of interest to note that GO and GN sheets tended to self-adjust their basal plane parallel to the substrate and form partially aligned layers. The sensitivity and working range were controlled by adjusting the GO content. By controlling the content of GO, GO/GN composite strain sensors were endowed with tunable sensitivity and stretchability. With an addition of 15 wt% GO, the gauge factor considerably increased by ~1400% from 10 (without addition of GO) to 153 under 7% stretching deformation. This reported fabrication method can be extended to other 2D materials for many emerging practical applications, such as artificial intelligence, electronic skins, personalized health monitoring and human-machine interface.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wearable strain sensors with high flexibility and sensitivity are becoming increasingly important because of their diverse applications in human-machine interfaces,[1] human motion detection,[2] electronic skins,[3-7] personalized health monitoring,[8] and soft robotics.[9] Many types of strain sensors based on Raman shifting, triboelectricity, fiber Bragg gratings, piezoelectricity, and capacitance have been developed. However, the limited stretching capacity of these sophisticated measurement devices and their low resolution make it challenging to implement them as strain sensors for wearable applications.[10-12] Piezoresistive sensors have, however, been widely used for strain sensors due to its simple read-out mechanism, superior sensitivity, and cost-effective fabrication.[10, 13, 14] Although traditional piezoresistive strain sensors based on semiconductors and metal foil can be cost-effective, most could not serve as wearable strain sensors due to their low sensitivity or narrow sensing range (<5%).[15] To develop stretchable and adequately sensitive strain sensors, various nanoscale materials including metal nanowires,[16, 17] nanoparticles,[18] silicon nanoribbons,[19] carbon black,[20] carbon nanofiber,[21] carbon nanotubes (CNTs),[2, 22-24] and graphene,[25-31] have been tested as alternative materials coupled with elastic polymers as a supporting substrate. Among them, low dimensional nanocarbon materials in the forms of films,[2, 28, 32, 33] meshes,[34, 35] fibers[30] and foams[36, 37] have attracted much attention due to their remarkable flexibility, conductivity and transparency compared with the alternatives.[15, 38]

Especially, graphene is an outstanding candidate for developing piezoresistive strain sensors due to its excellent electrical conductivity, unique optical properties, and high flexibility.[10, 13, 39] The hexagonal structure of a graphene sheet will be partially destroyed under applied tensile strain, altering

the electronic band structure and the electrical resistance.[40] But the sensitivity and stretchability of perfect graphene can be relatively low because the sensing mechanism mainly relies on the opening of bandgaps. For example, sensors using graphene grown through chemical vapor deposition (CVD) show gauge factors (GFs) of less than 14 with a maximum strain of ~7%.[41, 42] Several structural engineering strategies for increasing sensitivity and stretchability have been tested, including using nanographene,[29] graphene woven fabric,[34, 35, 43, 44] graphene foam,[36, 45-47] and graphene/polymer composites.[27, 28] Since smaller size graphene can offer more tunneling pathways, nanographene strain sensors have shown GFs exceeding 500.[29] However, they have a very limited strain range of 0–2%, greatly restricting their practical application. Graphene woven fabric is assembled by interweaving graphene ribbons. It also shows high sensitivity at very low strain (a GF of about 35 under 0.2% strain) with good repeatability.[35] Graphene foam with a microporous structure shows good stretchability up to 90%,[36, 48] but the change in resistance is relatively small, yielding poor sensitivity.[49] Graphite nanosheets (GNs) consisting of multilayered graphene can be easily produced *via* intercalation and expansion of natural graphite,[50, 51] but they have not been fully explored as a strategy to prepare low-cost strain sensors.

In this study, we employed an effective, facile and cost-efficient approach to prepare highly stretchable and sensitive GO/GN composite strain sensors with tunable sensitivity and stretchability by controlling the content of GO. The comprehensive performance of GO/GN strain sensors is comparable to that of the recently reported flexible strain sensors, simultaneously offering advantages of low-cost, simplicity, large-area compliance, as well as versatility in monitoring a wide range of strain (0-70%). To realize a fully integrated sensing system and extract information from body motions, we demonstrated versatile capabilities of GO/GN strain sensors as a wearable wireless pedometer, which opens up new opportunities for the widespread fabrication and application of strain-sensing devices.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Preparation of GO and GN

GO was synthesized based on our previous method.[51, 52] Graphite intercalated compound (GIC) was first prepared *via* the reaction of graphite with an intercalating agent of sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, 95.5-96.5%, General Chemical) and fuming nitric acid (HNO₃, Fisher) at room temperature with continuous stirring for 24 h. The dry GIC powder was thermally expanded at 1050 °C for 25 s to obtain GN. GO/GN mixtures with different contents of GO (0, 1, 5, 10, 15 wt%) were prepared by sonicating the foam in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) at 70 watts and 42 kHz for 2 h.

2.2 Fabrication of the strain sensor

The PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning) prepolymer was prepared by mixing base silicone gel and a curing agent at a 10:1 weight ratio, followed by degassing in a vacuum oven for 30 min. A pattern with a size of 3 mm × 20 mm was constructed on a clean glass slide (76 mm × 26 mm) by using scotch tape. The GO/GN solution was drop casted onto the patterned glass slide with a micropipette. After self-evaporation of IPA at room temperature, the self-aligned GO/GN hybrid thin films were formed. The liquid PDMS was poured onto the patterned glass slide in a petri dish using spin-coating. Then, it was cured at 65 °C for 1 h and the GO/GN-PDMS composite film was peeled off from the glass slide. Finally, the conductive silver paste was applied at both ends of composites as electrode for strain sensing performance characterization.

2.3 Device integration

We developed a fully integrated wearable pedometer by seamlessly interconnecting the GO/GN composite sensors, a Bluetooth module and a smartphone/laptop *via* a similar strategy with our previous design.[43, 47] The composite sensors were connected to a resistance analyser (DFR0339-Bluno beetle and HC06-Bluetooth Module), which was wirelessly monitored using an Android application or a custom-program. The data measured by the wearable sensors were transmitted to a smartphone through Bluetooth communication. For the wearable wireless pedometer, the Android app was designed and implemented in the MIT App Inventor development environment, which had three

main functions. (i) The raw data received from the sensors were displayed and stored automatically. (ii) The app could upload the collected results to the cloud for caregiver's access to data. (iii) The app was automatically directed to the motion of the person's knees that counted each step a person took.

2.4 Characterization

The morphologies of GO/GN composite thin films were characterized by the scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL JSM-6390F) and transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEOL 2010). Raman spectroscopy was performed using a Micro-Raman spectrometer (Renishaw Micro-Raman/Photoluminescence System) with the Ar ion laser at an excitation wavelength of 515 nm. The chemical state and the element composition of GO/GN composite thin films were determined with the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, PHI5600 Physical Electronics) using a monochromatic Al K α ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) as the excitation source. The data were analyzed using commercial software, CasaXPS, and a Shirley background fit. The universal testing machine (MTS Alliane RT-5) was used to measure the electromechanical properties by mounting the strain sensors on the custom-built stretching stage. The resistance of the composites under loading was collected simultaneously using a digital multimeter (34970A Data Acquisition/Data Logger Switch Unit, Agilent).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fabrication and characterization of GO/GN composite thin films

Figure 1a schematically illustrates the primary procedures of fabricating GO/GN composite strain sensors on a patterned glass slide. Rectangular patterns (3 mm \times 20 mm) were constructed using scotch tape adhered to a glass slide. GO/GN solution was drop casted onto the pattern followed by evaporation of IPA to form self-aligned GO/GN hybrid thin films. Upon peeling off the scotch tape, the patterned film was formed on the glass slide (**Figure 1b**). The liquid PDMS was then poured onto the glass substrate using spin-coating and the GO/GN-PDMS composite was obtained after curing the PDMS. After the film was peeled off from the glass slide, the conductive silver paste was applied at its both ends. The patterning with the scotch tape is very cost-effective and enables designing the sensing films in various shapes and sizes in a facile process. It can also be applied on other hydrophobic substrates that make scaled-up production and practical applications possible. In **Figure 1c**, the strain sensor was stretched by 70%, showing the high stretchability of the sensor.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration (a) and optical pictures (b, c) of the fabrication of GO/GN composite thin film strain sensors.

Figures 2a-b show representative TEM images of GN and GO/GN hybrid. Due to the strong hydrogen bonding and the van der Waals interactions, GO sheets adsorbed on the surface of the GN, which benefit the uniform distribution of GN in solution and final composite. Similar with our previous discoveries,[53, 54] both GN (**Figure 2c**) and GO/GN (**Figure 2d**) self-assembled into a layered structure due to the “excluded volume” interactions among the sheets. To further confirm the efficient adsorption of GO on the surface of GN, the Raman spectra of hybrid GO/GN and pure GN films were shown in **Figure 2e**. Typical D band at $\sim 1354\text{ cm}^{-1}$, G band at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 2D band at $\sim 2723\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed. The degree of defects in the GN was estimated by the intensity ratio of the D and G band (I_D/I_G). The GN had an I_D/I_G of 0.08, indicating less defects of GNs with the lattice structure of graphene. Moreover, I_D/I_G could reveal the amount of GO on GN through evaluating structural imperfections created by the attachment of GO. With the addition of 1, 5, 10 wt% GO, I_D/I_G was 0.23, 0.43 and 0.65 respectively, which was consistent with the increasing content of GO. Additionally, the XPS spectra of 10 wt% GO/GN (**Figure 2f**) shows that the carbon to oxygen ratios for GN, GO/GN and GO were ~ 21 , 11 and 1.5, respectively. The spectra of 10 wt% GO/GN and GO mainly consisted of three chemical components with C-C (red) in aromatic rings at 284.5 eV, C-O/C=O bonds (blue, such as hydroxyl, epoxy and carbonyl) at 286.7 eV, and O=C-O bonds (cyan, carboxyl) at 288.5 eV. The C-C was predominated and other oxygen containing peaks were not observed distinctively in GN.

Figure 2: Characterization of GN and GO/GN hybrid. (a-d) TEM (a, b) and SEM (c, d) images of GN (a), GO attached GN (b), GN thin films (c) and GO/GN composite thin film (d). (e) Raman spectra of GN and 1, 5, 10 wt% GO/GN films, respectively. (f) High resolution C 1s spectra of GN, 10 wt% GO/GN and GO, respectively.

3.2 Strain sensing performance

The strain sensing performance of GO/GN composite strain sensors was investigated by monitoring the resistance change under various strain levels. **Figure 3a** shows the dynamic response of the GO/GN strain sensors under applied tensile strains. It is found that the linearity, sensitivity and stretchability could be controlled by adjusting the contents of GO. With addition of 1 wt% GO, the GO/GN composite strain sensors did not show good linear response to strains, but the stretchability could reach up to 70% with slightly increased GF. On the other hand, the GO/GN composite strain sensors with 5, 10, 15 wt% GO showed better linear response and sensitivity, but the stretchability was sacrificed accordingly. For example, the GF of the 5, 10, 15 wt% GO/GN strain sensors was 30, 120 and 153 with a stretchability of 50, 15 and 7%, respectively. Compared to the pure GN strain sensors,

the GF of GO/GN considerably increased by ~1400% at 15 wt% GO addition with the GF increasing from 10 (without addition of GO) to 153. The composite strain sensors demonstrated here have several unique advantages, such as ease of tuning the GFs and stretchability to meet different requirements for different applications. In addition, as shown in **Figure 3b**, the sensors showed stable variation in resistance under cyclic strains of 5%. 10%, 20% and 40%, demonstrating good durability. Compared with other reported graphene-based assemblies, such as suspended graphene (GFs of ~1.9 at 3% strain),[40] graphene ripples (a negative GF of -2 with a stretchability of 30%),[25] graphene reinforced CNT networks (low GF of 0.36 with a stretchability of 10%),[55] fish-scale-like graphene (GF of 16.2 with a large stretchability to 60%),[38] graphene flakes (a large GF of 150 with a stretchability of 1.7%),[26] graphene aerogel (GF of 61.3 with a stretchability of 15%),[56] graphene foam (GF of 24 at 10% strain),[47] graphene woven fabric (larger GF of 223 at 3% strain),[43] polyethylenimine-rGO (ultra-high GF of 754 with a stretchability of 5%),[57] the GO/GN strain sensors simultaneously delivered an excellent linearity, sensitivity and stretchability. More importantly, a good trade-off between the sensitivity and stretchability was obtained with a facile fabrication approach.

Figure 3: Electromechanical performance of strain sensors. (a) Relative changes of resistance with different GO contents. (b) Dynamic response of the sensor to cyclic strain of 5%. 10%, 20% and 40% for 1wt% GO/GN strain sensors.

3.3 Sensing mechanism

To elucidate the sensing mechanism of GO/GN strain sensors, the microstructure evolution was monitored at the different strain levels. As shown in **Figure 4a-c**, the GO/GN film possessed three types of junctions between nanosheets, i.e., i) complete contact by overlapping, ii) partially overlapped flakes, and iii) disconnection caused by microcracks. A simple model was proposed based on the slippage and microcrack of nanomaterials in **Figure 4d**. In the initial state of stretching, the sliding between aligned GN reduced overlap area and thus the electrical resistance of the composite thin film was increased due to the less conduction paths. At large strains, the electron tunneling resistance induced by the microcrack was much larger than the contact resistance, resulting in much higher GF at higher strain.

Figure 4: SEM images of (a) the initial unstretched 10 wt% GO/GN, (b) after applying 10% strain and (c) after applying 20% strain. (d) Schematic illustration of sensing mechanism of strain sensors.

3.4 Wearable application

Given the high sensitivity, good linearity, excellent reproducibility of sensory capability of the GO/GN composites, it is very appealing to use them as highly sensitive motion sensors for emerging wearable applications. We developed a fully integrated, wireless, and wearable pedometer by seamlessly interconnecting the GO/GN strain sensors, a Bluetooth module and an external device like a smartphone, as shown in **Figure 5**. The on-body measurements were greatly facilitated by signal transduction, conditioning, processing and wireless transmission. The Bluno Beetle with programming and computational capabilities was able to analyze the resistance change of strain sensors. The piezoresistive signals generated from Bluno Beetle were transmitted over the wireless Bluetooth communication link, which was used to connect with external electronics. The smartphone displayed the real time signals acquired from the on-body measurements. The custom-designed Android application with a simple user-friendly interface saved the collected data in a text file, which could be shared through short message service, email, and uploaded to cloud servers. The mechanism of our pedometer relied on bending and relaxation of the sensors on the leg joint, resulting in a sharp increase and decrease of electrical resistance. Gait or walking pattern was a general indicator of an individual's health condition because the gait of patients is quite different from those of healthy individuals. Once the correlations between the gait signals and various diseases were identified, this feature was particularly useful for people who monitored their health conditions.

Figure 5: A wireless pedometer with a custom-developed app.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we reported an effective and facile approach to prepare highly stretchable and sensitive strain sensors based on the readily available GN and GO as sensing materials. A good trade-off between sensitivity and stretchability for the strain sensors was achieved attributed to a synergistic effect of two mechanisms. The variation of microcrack junctions under strain and contact-separation of GN conductive backbones due to the presence of GO greatly changed the microstructure of the conductive network. The high performance of GO/GN strain sensors surpassed majority of recent sensors of complicated designed architectures and possessed advantages of low-cost, simplicity, large-area compliance, as well as versatility in monitoring a wide range of strain. To realize a fully integrated sensing system and extract information from body motions, we demonstrated versatile capabilities of GO/GN strain sensors as a wearable wireless pedometer. This simple fabrication for high performance strain sensors sheds important light on the use of common nanomaterials to many emerging practical applications, such as artificial intelligence, electronic skins, personalized health monitoring and human-machine interface.

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